

Effect of Halloysite Nanotubes and Waste Chicken Feathers as Fire Retardants in Green Composites

Anil N. Netravali

Jean and Douglas McLean Professor of Fiber Science (Emeritus)

Dept. of Human Centered Design

ICCM 24

Baltimore, MD

August 4-8, 2025

Types of Composite Materials based on Reinforcement

(ASTM Standardization News)

Particulate Composite

Flake Composite

Random-Fiber Composite

Continuous Fiber Lamina Composite

Woven Lamina Composite

Braided Composite

Composite Applications - 1

Aerospace

White Night 2

Ground Transportation

Composite Applications - 2

Sports

Medical

Electronics

Composite Applications - 3

Civil and Structural

Housing

Production & Sales and Use of Resins

(US-2023)
(Millions of pounds)

Plastics	U.S. Production	Total Sales & Captive Use
Thermosets	17,470	17,547
Thermoplastics	118,554	118,761
TOTAL	136,024	136,308

Source: American Chemistry Council, March 2023

**Most Derived from Petroleum *Not Biodegradable*

**Not Sustainable *Not Environment-Friendly*

**About 94% of composites end up in landfills*

6-8% of Petroleum is used for producing Plastics, Polymers, Fibers, etc.

Today's Environmental 'Mantras'

OR

Guiding Principles

- **'Green' Chemistry**
- **Environment-Friendly, Fully Sustainable 'Green' Materials**
- **Recyclable Materials,**
- **'Cradle-to-Cradle' Design**
- **Life Cycle Assessment**
- **The 4 'R's**

LIFE CYCLE OF 'Green' Materials

A Purist's view

Biodegradable Resins

BIODEGRADABLE POLYMERS

Natural

1. **Polysaccharides**
 - **Starch** ✓
 - **Cellulose**
 - Chitin
 - Pullulan
 - Levan
 - Konjac
 - Elsinan
2. **Proteins**
 - Collagen/Gelatin
 - Casein, Albumin, Fibrogen, Silks, Elastins
 - **Protein from grains** ✓
3. **Polyesters**
 - **Polyhydroxyalkanoates** ✓
4. **Other Polymers**
 - Lignin
 - Shellac
 - Natural Rubber

Synthetic

1. **Poly(amides)**
2. **Poly(anhydrides)**
3. **Poly(amide-enamines)**
4. **Poly(vinyl alcohol)** ✓
5. **Poly(ethylene-co-vinyl alcohol)**
6. **Poly(vinyl acetate)**
7. **Polyesters**
 - Poly(glycolic acid)
 - Poly(lactic acid)
 - Poly(caprolactone)
 - Poly(ortho esters)
8. **Poly(ethylene oxide)**
9. **Some Poly(urethanes)**
10. **Poly(phosphazines)**
11. **Poly(imino carbomates)**
12. **Some Poly(acrylates)**

Why Soy Protein?

- **Plant-based resource**
- **Yearly renewable - Sustainable**
- **Fully Biodegradable**
- **Inexpensive and Worldwide Availability**
 - **SF, SPC, SPI**
- **Benign Process of Separating Protein**

Also

➤ **Multi-functional Protein**

Polar Amino Acids in Soy Protein

- **Aspartic acid (anionic)**
- **Glutamic acid (anionic)**
- **Arginine (cationic)**
- **Lysine (cationic)**
- **Histidine (cationic)**
- **Serine (hydroxyl)**
- **Threonine (hydroxyl)**
- **Tyrosine (hydroxyl)**
- **Cystine (sulfhydryl)**

Ways of Modifying Soy Protein as Resin

- **Cross-linking** ✓
- **Internal plasticization** ✓
- **Blending with other resins** ✓
- **Hydrophobicity Enhancers** ✓
- **Forming Interpenetrating Network (IPN) or IPN-like Structures** ✓
- **Nano-Composites with clay and other nano-particles and fibrils** ✓ □
- **Preparing self-healing resins** ✓ □
- **Improve Fire Performance**

✓ = Methods used in our lab

Some Natural Fibers-I

Banana

Pineapple

Henequen

Curaua

Bamboo

Flax

Bagasse

Some Natural Fibers-II

Jute

Kenaf

Sisal

Coconut

Hemp

Ramie

Engineering of Natural Fiber Composites

Resin process

Composite process

Tensile Properties of Flax Yarn/MSPI Composites

(Yarns kept under slight stress)
(45% yarn content by wt)

Composites	Fracture Stress (MPa)	Fracture Strain (%)	Young's Modulus (GPa)
Axial	256.4 (370.0)*	13.3	3.3
Transverse	10.2	3.0	0.6

*Strength estimated for 65% fiber content

Much stronger than wood and wood products and
- can be engineered
- can be molded

Chabba, Matthews and Netravali, Green Chemistry - 2005
Chabba and Netravali, Part 1 &2, J Mater. Sci. - 2005
Lodha and Netravali, Polymer Composites – 2005
Nam and Netravali, Part 1 & 2, Fibers Polymers – 2006
Huang and Netravali, Comp. Sci. Tech., - 2009
Kim and Netravali, Composites A. – 2010
Kim and Netravali, J. Ag Food Chem. - 2010

Use of 'Green' Composites at Cornell University

**Fire Resistance of Soy Protein-based
Green Composites
with
Halloysite Nanotubes (HNT)
(Cone Calorimetry)**

Photographic Images of Torching Jute-Soy Protein Corrugated Composites

Fabrication of Layered Green Composites

Jute Fabric + Soy Protein + HNT

Raw HNT

Soy Protein Concentrate

Reinforcing Jute Fabric

TEM Image of
SPC Resin with HNT

Photograph of
Jute-SPC-HNT
Layered Composite
(after 3-point bend test)

Heat Release Rate and Char Remains (Cone Calorimetry)

Chars of Jute-SPC (Control) Composites

Chars of Jute-SPC-HNT Composites

HRR of Jute-SPC Composites

HRR of Jute-SPC-HNT Composites

Cone Calorimeter Summary Data: Jute-SPC-HNT Composite Specimens

Sample Description	Sample Thickness (mm)	Time to ignition (s)	Peak HRR (kW/m ²)	Time to Peak HRR (s)	Starting Mass (g)	Total Mass Loss (g)	Weight % Lost (%)	Total Heat Release (MJ/m ²)	Total smoke Release (m ² /m ²)	MAHRE (kW/m ²)	FIGRA
Control	5.4	47	319	274	64.4	51.7	80.3	73.1	505	190	1.16
Sample	5.4	38	341	297	58.3	47.7	81.8	66.4	448	177	1.15
	5.7	48	382	292	68.9	55.0	79.8	76.3	411	193	1.31
Average Data	5.5	44	347	288	63.9	51.5	80.7	71.9	455	187	1.21
10% HNT	6.6	32	363	49	69.8	54.0	77.4	73.3	431	168	7.41
+ glycerol	6.3	32	315	52	72.9	56.1	77.0	75.7	392	168	6.06
	6.3	48	392	65	73.9	57.5	77.8	80.6	390	169	6.03
Average Data	6.4	37	357	55	72.2	55.9	77.4	76.5	404	168	6.50
10% HNT	6.5	34	332	50	68.4	53.5	78.3	73.8	326	167	6.63
	6.2	36	287	52	68.1	51.8	76.1	69.0	307	162	5.52
Average Data	6.3	35	309	51	68.2	52.7	77.2	71.4	316	164	6.08
no HNT	5.5	45	439	299	67.5	55.6	82.4	81.6	351	214	1.47
+ glycerol	5.6	43	341	321	67.0	54.7	81.7	76.7	448	196	1.06
	5.4	57	401	367	69.7	55.9	80.2	80.5	400	191	1.09
Average Data	5.5	48	394	329	68.0	55.4	81.4	79.6	399	200	1.21

Conclusions on Fire Performance of Green Composites

- **Proteins do not burn easily**
 - **Have lot of nitrogen**
 - **Contain Moisture (6 to 10%)**
 - **When heated OH and COOH groups react with NH_2 to create H_2O**
- **Protein-based composites perform better than some synthetic composites (e.g. ester-based and some epoxy-based)**
- **Plenty of opportunity to improve the performance further using green fire retardants**

**Fire Resistance of Soy Protein-based
Green Composites
With
Chicken Feather Fibers (CFF)
(Microscale Cone Calorimetry)**

CFF – Agricultural Background

- Industrial poultry processing produces **over 400 million metric tons of chicken feather waste** (feathers, blood, feces) internationally
- Currently, **most of this waste is either being landfilled or incinerated**, both are detrimental to the environment
- **Feathers contain high amounts of keratin (~ 91%)**, allowing for the synthesis of organic resins and composites

CFF – Morphology

- **Hierarchical structure:** quills (CFQ), barbs (CFB), barbules, and hooklets
- CFQ primarily β sheet protein conformation, CFB primarily α helix \rightarrow leads to differences in mechanical properties, hydrophilicity, etc.

***In the current research we used all parts of feather in chopped form**

MCC Results for CFF/SPI Resins

Microscale Cone Calorimetry (MCC) Results for CFF/Soy Protein-based Resins

- **Mean pHRR increases with CFF, lower for resins wGA (X-linked)**

- Mean TpHRR decreases with CFF, higher for resins wGA

- **Mean THR lowest for 10/20% CFF, lower without GA**

	0/100	10/90	20/80	30/70	0/100 wGA	10/90 wGA	20/80 wGA	30/70 wGA
pHRR (W/g)	101 (13.5)*	112 (6.46)	118 (16.1)	120 (11.5)	94.5 (5.02)	107 (12.4)	114 (6.28)	114 (12.2)
TpHRR (C°)	331 (1.91)	331 (1.79)	330 (2.83)	329 (1.32)	336 (2.59)	333 (1.35)	334 (1.41)	327 (1.51)
THR (kJ/g)	13.9 (59.5)	9.38 (7.60)	9.99 (4.1)	18.2 (47.6)	11.9 (5.36)	10.8 (4.14)	13.6 (34.9)	11.2 (6.09)
Char Yield (%)	24.7 (2.85)	25.1 (0.782)	28.7 (3.6)	25.0 (3.50)	23.4 (2.72)	23.7 (0.781)	25.4 (6.50)	25.2 (18.3)

MCC Results for Soy Protein-based Resins

- **CFF potentially promote high quality char formation, until a critical ratio (10-20%) due to smoldering**
- **CFF moisture content between ~ 10%, SPI moisture content ~ 5%**
- **Through synergistic crosslinking, GA promotes high quality char layers, quality suffers with addition of CFF**

MCC Results for JF-CFF/SPI Composites

MCC Results for Composites

- Composites have lower mean pHRR and THR than resins → **Impact of JF?**
- GA did not reduce mean pHRR and THR (unlike in resins)
- Mean pHRR and THR optimized with ~ 20% CFF

	0/100	10/90	20/80	30/70	0/100 wGA	10/90 wGA	20/80 wGA	30/70 wGA
pHRR (W/g)	83.1 (1.41)*	87.7 (5.50)	81.1 (1.99)	94.5 (10.5)	92.8 (6.87)	97.4 (20.7)	86.0 (9.67)	99.3 (2.24)
TpHRR (°C)	336 (0.205)	336 (0.323)	330 (1.38)	332 (1.68)	332 (1.75)	336 (0.922)	332 (1.13)	332 (1.62)
THR (kJ/g)	8.71 (15.3)	10.7 (21.6)	7.72 (3.28)	12.3 (24.6)	10.4 (3.52)	15.8 (63.4)	8.14 (10.6)	10.2 (6.23)
Char Yield (%)	23.7 (5.64)	25.9 (3.67)	28.7 (3.76)	25.5 (10.9)	23.5 (0.799)	25.6 (2.77)	25.2 (2.3)	25.2 (2.36)

MCC Results for JF-CFF/Soy-based Composites

- JF, like CFF, likely promotes better quality char to reduce flammability
- CFF synergizes with JF to decrease flammability through compact char formation → controls burning
- GA shows slightly higher flammability for composites (unlike resin) likely due to lower quality char formation?
- While the effect of CFF may not be very large, it still helps
- **We can use CFF up to 20% in the resin with beneficial effect**

Acknowledgements

• **Ms. R. Nakamura**

Dr. A. B. Morgan

Dr. M. R. Nyden

• **Dr. J. W. Gilman**

Dr. R. A. Mensah

Dr. O. Das

• **Mr. A. N. Shankar**

Materials

Prof. J. Barone

Archer Daniels Midland (ADM)

Funding/Facilities

• **NSF**

• **Cornell Tata Institute**

• **CCMR**

Questions?

